

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation Optimization & Evaluation of Co-Processed Excipients for Orally Disintegrating Tablet of Bilastine

Pranjal Borse*, Manoj Bari

Shree Sureshdada Jain Institute of Pharmaceutical education & Research, Jamner 424206, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 June 2025

Keywords:

Co-Processed excipients,
Solvent Evaporation
Method, CCD, Bilastine
ODT

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15710893

ABSTRACT

The development of novel excipients with enhanced functionality has been explored through particle engineering techniques such as co-processing. This study aimed to improve the direct compression properties of banana powder by co-processing it with microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) in optimized proportions using the solvent evaporation method. The resulting co-processed excipient (CPE) was evaluated for its flow and compaction properties in comparison to its individual components and their physical mixture. Orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) containing 20 mg of Bilastine were formulated using the optimized CPE via direct compression. The tablets were assessed for critical quality attributes, including Flowability, compressibility, disintegration time, and drug release. Application of Design of Experiments (DoE) using Central Composite Design (CCD) enabled effective optimization of the excipient composition. The optimized batch (CPE5) showed excellent performance with an angle of repose of 25.32°, Carr's index of 15.57%, Hausner's ratio of 1.1557, disintegration time of 10.5 seconds, drug content of 96.86%, and drug release of Bilastine is 94.53% within 10 minutes, confirming its suitability for or dispersible tablet formulations. The optimized co-processed formulation demonstrated superior performance, with significantly improved disintegration and mechanical properties compared to conventional blends. The study concludes that co-processing banana powder with MCC successfully enhanced its functionality for use in direct compression and offers a robust platform for the development of fast-disintegrating Bilastine tablets.

INTRODUCTION

Co-processed excipients (CPEs) have gained significant attention in pharmaceutical formulation due to their ability to overcome the

limitations of individual excipients. Unlike simple physical mixtures, co-processed excipients are engineered combinations of two or more existing excipients, designed to provide synergistic

***Corresponding Author:** Pranjal Borse

Address: Shree Sureshdada Jain Institute of Pharmaceutical education & Research, Jamner 424206, Maharashtra, India.

Email ✉: borsepranjal38@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

improvements in flowability, compressibility, and functional performance without compromising the stability or efficacy of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). This approach is particularly valuable in the development of orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs), where rapid disintegration, mechanical strength, and patient acceptability are critical. In the present study, co-processed excipients were developed using banana powder a natural, biodegradable excipient with good swelling properties and microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), a well-established binder and filler with excellent compressibility. The co-processing was carried out using the solvent evaporation method to enhance compatibility and improve powder characteristics. The main objective was to formulate and optimize a novel ODT of Bilastine, an antihistaminic agent, by utilizing these co-processed excipients. To achieve this, a Central Composite Design (CCD) under Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was employed to evaluate the effect of varying concentrations of banana powder and MCC on critical formulation parameters such as angle of repose, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and disintegration time. By optimizing the CPE composition, the study aims to improve not only the manufacturing efficiency but also the functional performance of the ODT, ensuring rapid disintegration and effective drug release for enhanced patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

MATERIALS:

Bilastine (Medley Pharma Ltd ; Andheri) , Banana Powder (Nutribud Foods Pvt.Ltd.) , MCC (Jinendra Scientifics ;Jalgaon), Orange Flavor(Marc Flavors ,Greater Noida), Aspartame(Jinendra Scientifics ;Jalgaon), Aerosil (Medley

Pharma Ltd ; Andheri),Magnesium Stearate (Loba Chemie;Mumbai).

Preformulation study: ⁽⁴⁾

Determination of UV Spectrum of Bilastine:

Bilastine solution (10 ug/ml) was prepared in phosphate buffer pH 6.8. This solution scanned under double beam UV visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1800) and spectrum was recorded in the wavelength ranges between 200 - 400 nm. Spectrum was shown in Fig. No. 2.

Standard Calibration Curve of Bilastine:

Weigh accurately 10 mg of Bilastine, transfer it into 100 ml volumetric flask add phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to obtained concentration 100 ug/ml. From this solution, pipette out 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 & 2.5ml, transfer each to 10 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to 10 ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get 5, 10, 15, 20 & 25 ug/ml concentration of Bilastine respectively. Absorbance of each solution was measured at 282 nm using UV visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800) and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as reference standard and the standard curve was generated. The standard calibration curve shown in Fig.No.3

Drug Excipient Compatibility Study: ^(7,9,12)

• Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy:

Fourier transformed infrared technique was one of the most powerful techniques was identify functional groups. The FTIR analysis method uses infrared light to scan test samples and observe chemical properties. The FTIR studies were carried out using FTIR 1-5 Affinity. The Potassium bromide disc method used for preparation of the sample. The infrared spectrum

of pure Bilastine, CPE, Bilastine+ CPE were showed in fig no. 4,5&6

- **DSC Analysis:**

DSC is one of the most common analytical techniques used to characterize pharmaceutical solids. This technique is used to study what happens to polymers/ samples upon heating Drug and excipients in the ratio 1:1 was analyzed for DSC. The DSC spectrum of pure Bilastine were showed in fig no. 7 and the DSC spectrum of CPE were shown in fig no. 8 and the DSC spectrum of mixture of Bilastine with CPE were shown in fig no.9 respectively

Method of Preparation:

Preparation of Co-Processed Excipients Using Solvent Evaporation method: ⁽¹²⁾

Firstly, weigh all ingredients properly. Dissolve the banana powder in water to form a slurry. Gradually add the weighed MCC to the banana slurry while stirring continuously to ensure uniform mixing. Heat the slurry gently to allow the solvent (water) to evaporate. Once most of the solvent has evaporated transfer the mixture to a hot air oven maintained at 40°C-60°C for drying. When the mixture becomes semi-dry, pass it through a 22# mesh to obtain granules. Finally, dry the granules again until the desired moisture content is achieved.

Fig. CPE of Banana Powder +MCC

Preparation of Tablet: ⁽⁵⁾

Weigh all ingredients properly. Pass the drug (Bilastine) #60 mesh and CPE through a #22 mesh sieve. Pass aspartame orange flavour through #60 mesh sieve. Add the magnesium stearate and aerosil into a above blend and mixed them properly in a polybag. Weigh 200 mg of the prepared tablet blend and compress it using a KBr Press fitted with an 8mm punch.

Optimization: ^(6,7)

Optimization of the formulation was carried out using a statistical approach to identify the most suitable composition of co-processed excipients (CPE) for Bilastine orally disintegrating tablets (ODT). The Central Composite Design (CCD), a response surface methodology under the Design of Experiments (DOE) software, was employed for this purpose. Two independent formulation variables—concentration of banana powder (X_1) and concentration of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC, X_2)—were selected for optimization. Their effects were studied on four dependent response variables: angle of repose (Y_1), Carr's index (Y_2), Hausner's ratio (Y_3), and disintegration time (Y_4). These responses were chosen as indicators of powder flow properties and tablet performance.

Table 1: Independent Variables & Their Levels in CCD

Independent Variables	Unit	Level				
		- α	Low	Medium	High	+ α
Banana Powder	%	54.8223	60	72.50	85	90.1777
MCC	%	9.82233	15	27.50	40	45.1777

Table 2: Dependent Variables with Their Actual Coded Values

Response Variable	Actual Coded Values	Unit
Angle of Repose	Y1	O
Carr's Index	Y2	%
Hausner's Ratio	Y3	%
Disintegration Time	Y4	Sec

Table 3: Composition of Co-Processed Excipients Batches Generated by CCD

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Batches									
		CPE1	CPE2	CPE3	CPE4	CPE5	CPE6	CPE7	CPE8	CPE9	CPE10
1	Banana Powder	9.018	7.25	5.482	8.5	7.25	6	7.25	8.5	7.25	6
2	MCC	2.75	2.75	2.75	1.5	2.75	4	4.518	4	0.982	1.5
3	Water	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.
Average Wt.		10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

All Ingredients are in gm.

Table 4: Composition of Bilastine ODT Using Co-Processed Excipients Generated by CCD

Ingredients	Batches									
	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10
Bilastine	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
CPE	166 (F1)	166 (F2)	166 (F3)	166 (F4)	166 (F5)	166 (F6)	166 (F7)	166 (F8)	166 (F9)	166 (F10)
Orange Flavour	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Aspartame	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Aerosil	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Mg. Stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Avg. Wt.	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

All Ingredients are in mg.

Evaluation Parameter of Co-Processed Excipients & Tablets:

Pre-Compression Parameter of Co-Processed Excipients: ⁽¹⁷⁾

1. Bulk Density:

It is the ratio of total mass of powder to the bulk volume of powder. It was measured by pouring the weighed powder (passed through standard sieve #20) into a measuring cylinder and initial weight was noted. This initial volume is called the bulk volume. From this the bulk density is calculated

according to the formula mentioned below. It is expressed in g/ml and is given by:

$$BD = \frac{\text{Mass of the Powder (M)}}{\text{Bulk Volume of the Powder (Vb)}}$$

2. Tapped Density

It is the ratio of total mass of the powder to the tapped volume of the powder. Volume was measured by tapping the powder for 750 times and the tapped volume was noted if the difference between these two volumes is less than 2%. If it is more than 2%, tapping is continued for 1250 times and tapped volume was noted. Tapping was continued until the difference between successive volumes is less than 2% (in a bulk density apparatus).

$$TD = \frac{\text{Mass of the Powder (M)}}{\text{Tapped Volume of the Powder (Vd)}}$$

3. Carr's Index:

Compressibility index (CI) was determined by measuring the initial volume (VO) and final volume (V) after hundred tapings of a sample in a measuring cylinder. CI was calculated using equation:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{V_0 - V}{V} \times 100$$

4. Hausner's Ratio:

A similar index to indicate the flow properties can be defined by Hausner's ratio. Hausner's ratio can be calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density}}{\text{Bulk Density}}$$

5. Angle of Repose:

Angle of repose was determined by using funnel method. The accurately weighed blend was taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a way that the tip of the funnel just touches the apex of the heap of blend. The drug (as solid dispersion) excipients blend was allowed to flow through the funnel freely on to the surface. The diameter of the powder cone was measured and angle of repose was calculated using the following equation:

$$\tan \theta = \frac{h}{r}$$

Post-Compression Parameter of Tablets: ^(15,17)

1. Hardness:

The tablet crushing strength was determined using a Monsanto hardness tester. Three tablets were randomly sampled from each formulation batch, and the average reading was recorded.

2. Weight variation:

To determine variation 20 tablets of each formulation were individually weighed using an electronic balance. The average weight was calculated and the individual tablet weight was then compared to the average value.

3. Friability:

A total of 10 tablets were accurately weighed and placed in the drum of the friabilator. The instrument was operated at 25 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 4 minutes, making a total of 100

revolutions. After the test, the tablets were dedusted using a soft brush, and the final weight was recorded.

4. Thickness:

Tablet thickness is a crucial element in both duplicating appearance and counting with filling machinery the uniform thickness of the tablets is used as a counting mechanism by some filling equipment micrometer was used to measure thickness.

5. Disintegration Test:

The disintegration time is the release rate of the active ingredients from the tablets. The disintegration times can be recorded utilizing USP tablet disintegration apparatus during this test. The time taken for the suppository to melt or disperse is when immersed in a water bath maintained at constant temp (37 ± 20 C). The time required for the tablet to melt or dispersed in the surrounding water was noted. Unless intended for modified release or for prolonged local action. They comply the test for disintegration of tablets.

6. Drug Content:

ODT containing 20mg of the drug was made to dissolve in 100ml of the buffer pH6.8 and then absorbance were measured at 282 nm using UV spectrophotometer and the amount of the drug present was calculated using the calibration curve.

7. Wetting Time:

Take a double folded tissue paper was placed in a petri dish containing 6 ml of methylene blue solution. Then the tablet was placed on tissue paper containing methylene blue and the time required for complete wetness of tablet was recorded as wetting time the randomly three

tablets were chosen from each formulation and the average wetting time was recorded.

8. In-Vitro Dissolution Study: ⁽⁶⁾

The in-vitro dissolution study of Bilastine orodispersible tablets (ODT) was conducted using a dissolution tester (USP TDL-08L) equipped with a USP Type II paddle apparatus. The study utilized phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as the dissolution medium, with a volume of 900 ml maintained at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C to simulate physiological conditions. The paddle rotation speed was set at 50 rpm to ensure consistent mixing. Drug concentration was determined spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 282 nm. At specified time intervals, 5 ml aliquots were withdrawn from the dissolution vessel and immediately replaced with fresh buffer to maintain sink conditions. The amount of drug dissolved at each time point was calculated and expressed as a percentage of the total drug content. These values were then plotted against time to generate a dissolution profile, allowing for analysis of the release kinetics of Bilastine from the orodispersible tablets.

9. Stability Study:

Stability studies were conducted over a period of 30 days under accelerated conditions of $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ RH. During this period, the orodispersible tablet (ODT) were evaluated for any alterations in various parameters such as average weight, hardness, thickness, friability disintegration time, drug content, drug release percentage, and other relevant characteristics. The Bilastine ODT remained both physically and chemically stable, exhibiting no significant changes in their physical attributes. Among the formulations, B5 maintained its integrity and original properties, with only slight variations

observed in above parameters, all of which remained within acceptable limits.

Preformulation Study:

Determination of UV Spectrum of Bilastine:

RESULT & DISCUSSION:

Fig No.2: UV Spectrum of Bilastine

Standard Calibration Curve of Bilastine:

Table No. 5: Observation Table for Calibration Curve of Bilastine

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (nm)
---------	-----------------------	-----------------

1	0	0
2	5	0.101
3	10	0.142
4	15	0.223
5	20	0.296
6	25	0.373

Fig.No.3: Calibration Curve of Bilastine

Drug Excipient Compatibility Study:

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy:

Fig.No. 4 FTIR Spectrum of Bilastine

Fig. No. 5 FTIR Spectrum of CPE

Fig. No.6 FTIR Spectrum of Bilastine +CPE

DSC Analysis:

Fig. No.7 DSC Analysis of Bilastine

Fig.No. 8. DSC Analysis of CPE

Fig.No. 9. DSC Analysis of Bilastine+CPE

Pre-Compression Parameter :

Bulk Density:

Bulk Density of optimized batches of CPE was found in the range of 0.2941g/ml to 0.4545 g/ml. Results are shown in table no.6

Tapped Density:

Tapped Density of optimized batches of CPE was found in the range of 0.3263g/ml to 0.51g/ml. Results are shown in table no.6

Carr's Index :

Carr's Index of Optimized batches of CPE was found in the range of 9.870% to 20.184%. Results are shown in table no.6

Hausners Ratio:

Hausners Ratio of Optimized batches of CPE was found in the range of 1.09 to 1.201. Results are shown in table no.6

Angle of Repose:

Angle of Repose of optimized batches of CPE was found in the range of 13.82° to 29.68°. Results are Shown in table no.6

Table No.6 Pre-compression Parameter of CPE Generated by CCD:

Micromeritic Properties	Batches									
	CPE 1	CPE 2	CPE3	CPE4	CPE5	CPE6	CPE7	CPE8	CPE9	CPE10
Bulk Density	0.416	0.30	0.3125	0.4545	0.303	0.3125	0.2941	0.3333	0.454	0.454
Tapped Density	0.4848	0.3501	0.3756	0.51	0.3501	0.3491	0.3263	0.3662	0.5166	0.5
Carr's Index(%)	16.37	15.57	20.184	12.011	15.57	16.712	13.94	9.870	16.66	17.97
Hausner's Ratio	1.163	1.1557	1.201	1.1201	1.1557	1.167	1.139	1.09	1.166	1.17
Angle of Repose	23.62	25.32	29.68	18.43	25.32	24.30	21.80	28.98	13.82	22.75

Post-Compression Parameter of Tablets:

Hardness:

Hardness of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 1.6±1.5 to 1.9±0.5. Results are shown in table no.7

Weight variation:

Weight Variation of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 194±2 to 200±3. Results are shown in table no.7

Friability:

Friability of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 0.4±0.06 to 0.60±0.035. Results are shown in table no.7

Thickness:

Thickness of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 3.66 to 4.80. Results are shown in table no.7

Disintegration Test :

Disintegration Time of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 9.05 to 15.20 . Results are shown in table no.7

Drug Content:

Drug Content in Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 93.23 to 102.32 . Results are shown in table no. 7

Wetting Time:

Wetting Time of Bilastine ODT was found in the range of 10 to 28.06 . Results are shown in table no.7

In Vitro Dissolution Test:

Drug Release of Bilastine ODT within 10 min was found in the range of 88.84 to 108.50. results are shown in table no. 8

Table No.7 post-compression parameter of Bilastine ODT using Optimized CPE generated by CCD

Batches	Evaluation Parameter							
	Hardness	Weight Variation	Friability	Thickne ss	Disintegration Time	Drug Content	Wetting Time	% DR
B1	1.8±1	198.6±2.4	0.49±0.02	4	15.20	93.23	10	91.11
B2	1.7±0.1	196±2	0.50±0.06	3.90	10.15	96.86	18.45	94.53
B3	1.5±0.1	194±0	0.43±0.02	4.20	9.05	100.18	13.30	88.84
B4	1.9±0.2	197±3	0.60±0.035	3.96	12.28	97	28.06	93.39
B5	1.7±0.1	196±2	0.50±0.2	3.90	10.01	96.86	18.45	94.53
B6	1.6±1	194±2	0.52±0.032	4.80	9.07	102.32	20.45	98.80
B7	1.8±1	199±1	0.50±0	3.66	9.08	98.86	11	96.03
B8	1.6±1.5	194.6±16	0.40±0.06	3.96	11.08	99.30	20.01	97.95
B9	1.6±0.1	198±0	0.49±0.03	4.15	13.12	97.36	10.08	102.50
B10	1.6±1	200±3	0.46±0.05	3.60	10.12	98.23	23.28	96.81

All the values were in mean ±SD, n=3

Table No. 8 Percentage Drug Release of Bilastine ODT:

Time (Min)	Batches									
	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	36.44	39.86	41	51.25	39.86	42	52.30	46.69	64.92	45.55
4	59.22	62.64	48.97	59.22	62.64	58.30	60	61.50	74.03	60.36
6	66.06	70.61	67.20	74.03	70.61	72.82	78.66	70.61	87.70	71.75
8	82	87.70	74.03	86.56	87.70	86.88	88.20	86.56	94.53	88.84
10	91.11	94.53	88.84	93.39	94.53	98.80	96.03	97.95	102.50	96.81

Fig No. In-Vitro Drug Release Profile of Optimized Batches Bilastine ODT(B1-B10)

Data Analysis: ⁽⁷⁾

Angle of Repose:

Following regression equation could describe the Angle of Repose response,

$$\text{Angle of Repose (Y1)} = + 33.2 - 2.1X1 - 1.4X2$$

Concerning Disintegration, the results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the coefficients X1 and X2 bear a negative sign. The negative sign of X1 and X2 indicate an inverse relationship with response Y1 (Angle of repose). It reveals that the concentration of Banana Powder and MCC shows a reducing effect on Angle of repose. As the concentration of both X1 and X2 increases, the response Y1 (Angle of Repose) decreases, which is desirable for Good Flowability. ANOVA was used to identify the significant effect. The result was found to be significant at that level of probability.

Carr's Index:

Following regression equation could describe the Carr's Index response,

$$\text{Carr's Index (Y2)} = + 15.45 - 2.28X1 - 0.8445X2$$

Concerning Disintegration, the results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the coefficients X1 and X2 bear a negative sign. The negative sign of X1 and X2 indicate an inverse relationship with response Y1 (Carr's Index). It reveals that the concentration of Banana Powder and MCC shows a reducing effect on Angle of repose. As the concentration of both X1 and X2 increases, the response Y2 (Carr's Index) decreases, which is desirable for better powder flow properties. ANOVA was used to identify the significant effect. The result was found to be significant at that level of probability.

Hausner's Ratio:

Following regression equation could describe the Hausner's ratio response,

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio (Y3)} = + 1.14 - 0.0237X1 - 0.0095X2$$

Concerning Disintegration, the results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the coefficients X1 and X2 bear a negative sign. The negative sign of X1 and X2 indicate an inverse relationship with response Y3 (Hausner's Ratio). It reveals that the concentration of Banana Powder and MCC shows a reducing effect on Angle of repose. As the concentration of both X1 and X2 increases, the response Y3 (Hausners Ratio) decreases, which is desirable for better powder flow properties. ANOVA was used to identify the significant effect. The result was found to be significant at that level of probability.

Disintegration Time:

Following regression equation could describe the Disintegration Time response,

$$\text{Disintegration Time (Y4)} = + 20.4 - 2.2X1 - 1.6X2$$

Concerning Disintegration, the results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the coefficients X1 and X2 bear a negative sign. The negative sign of X1 and X2 indicate an inverse relationship with response Y4 (Disintegration Time). It reveals that the concentration of Banana Powder and MCC shows a reducing effect on angle of repose. As the concentration of both X1 and X2 increases, the response Y4 (Disintegration Time) decreases, which reduces Disintegration Time. ANOVA was used to identify the significant effect. The result was found to be significant at that level of probability.

Graphical Representation:

Fig No. Effect of Independent Factors X1& X2 On four dependent factors Y1, Y2, Y3 & Y4
 (a), (b), (c)&(d) indicates Response Surface Contour Graph Showing the Influence of Banana Powder(X1) and MCC (X2) on Angle of Repose (Y1), Carr's Index (Y2) & Hausner's ratio (Y3) & Disintegration Time (Y4). (e), (f), (g)&(h) indicates Response Surface 3D Graph Showing the Influence of Banana Powder(X1)

and MCC (X2) on Angle of Repose (Y1), Carr's Index (Y2) & Hausner's ratio (Y3) & Disintegration Time(Y4)

Stability Study:

Table No.9 Stability Study of Optimized Batch of Bilastine ODT:

Parameter		Condition		
		Initial	15 days	30 days
Physical	Avg. Wt.(mg)	196	196	196
	Thickness(mm)	3.90	3.90	3.88
	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	1.7	1.6	1.6
	Friability (% w/w)	0.50	0.48	0.47
Chemical	DT (Sec)	10.5	10.5	12
	%Drug Release	94.53	94.48	94.45
	Drug Content	96.86	96.85	96.84

CONCLUSION:

The present research successfully developed and optimized co-processed excipients (CPE) comprising banana powder and microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) to enhance the performance of orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) of Bilastine. Co-processing was carried out using a solvent evaporation method, and optimization was done using a Central Composite Design (CCD) to evaluate the influence of independent variables on key tablet properties. The batch optimized through Central Composite Design (CCD), specifically batch CPE5, showed favorable powder flow and tablet performance. The angle of repose was found to be 25.32°, indicating good flowability, while Carr's index and Hausner's ratio were 15.57% and 1.1557 respectively, confirming excellent compressibility and packing ability. The disintegration time of the tablet was observed to be 10.5 seconds, ensuring rapid onset of action, and the drug release was 94.53% within 10 minutes in phosphate buffer pH 6.8, which is within acceptable limits for immediate-release dosage forms. The drug content was consistent at 96.86%, ensuring dose uniformity. Other physical characteristics of the optimized batch included an average weight of 196 mg, tablet thickness of 3.90

mm, hardness of 1.7 kg/cm², and friability of 0.50% w/w, all within the pharmacopeial standards. Furthermore, a short-term stability study conducted over 30 days revealed no significant changes in the tablet properties, with disintegration time slightly increasing to 12 seconds and drug release and content remaining stable at 94.45% and 96.84%, respectively. These results confirm that the optimized co-processed excipients enhance the overall performance of Bilastine ODTs, offering a robust and patient-friendly formulation.

REFERENCES

1. S. B. Pawar, S. P. Ahirrao, S. J. Kshirsagar, "Review On Novel Pharmaceutical Coprocessed Excipients", *Pharmaceutical Resonance*, 2019 Vol.2 - Issue 1,14-20.
2. B. Mamatha, D. Srilatha, C. H. Sivanarayani, Prasanna Kumar Desu and P. Venkateswara Rao "Co-Processed Excipients: An Overview", *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2019, Volume 6, Issue 15, 224-237.

3. Ujwala Desai, Rohini Chavan, Priti Mhatre, Ruchika Chinchole, "A Review : Coprocessed Excipients", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review And Research*, 2012, Vol 12, Issue 2, 93-105.
4. N. K. Jain, *Pharmaceutical Product Development*, Second Edition, CBS Publishers and Distributors Pvt. Ltd. 251-316.
5. Vihong Qiu, Yisheng Chen, Geoff G. Z. Zhang, 'Developing Solid Oral Dosage Forms', 2011 Published by Elsevier, A Division of Reed Elsevier India Private Limited,; 167-170.
6. Umesh V. Bankar, *Pharmaceutical Dissolution Testing*, Informa Health Care, New York London, vol- 49.280-285.
7. Bolton Sanford. 'Pharmaceutical Statistics', Third Edition, James Swarbrick, North Carolina, 336-338.
8. Fatima Haruna, Yonni Eshovo Apeji, Avosuahi Rukayat Oyi, "Development and Characterization of a Microcrystalline Cellulose-based Co-Processed Excipient using Design of Experiment Approach", *Jordan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Volume 15, No. 4, 2022.
9. Lachman G. M. Pavia D. C. Kriz. G. S. and Vyvyan, 'IR Spectroscopy', Fourth Edition, 2014, Cengage Learning India Pvt. Ltd. Delhi: 29-73.
10. Ales Franc, David Vetchy, Pavlina Vodackova, Roman Kubalak, Lenka Jendrykova, Roman Gonec, "Co-processed Excipients For Direct Compression of Tablets", *Ces. slov. Pharm.* 2018; 67, 175–181.
11. Monika Tomar*, Amit Raj Sinha, Ajay Kumar Singh, "Process and Development of Co-Processed Excipient Silicified Microcrystalline Cellulose and Manufacture Paracetamol Tablet by Direct Compression", *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 42(1), 2017; 191-196.
12. Barbara Stuart, "Biological Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Wiley India Pvt. Ltd., 25-33.
13. Raymond C Rowe, Paul J. Sheskey, and Sian C. Owen, *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipient*, 5th edition, 346, 545-550.
14. V. Dinesh kumar, Ira Sharma and Vipin Sharma, "A Comprehensive Review On Fast Dissolving Tablet Technology", *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 2011 01 (05): 50-58.
15. Nani Parfati, Karina Citra Rani, Nathanael Charles, Valencia Geovanny, "Preparation and Evaluation of Atenolol- β -Cyclodextrin Orally Disintegrating Tablets Using Co-Process Crospovidone-Sodium Starch Glycolate", *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, 2018, Vol 10, Issue 5, 190-194.
16. Sunil Aute, S B Shirsand, Shailashri, Amruta and S A Baig, "Development of Novel Co Processed Excipients For The Design Of Fast Dissolving Tablets", *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2019, 457-462.
17. Olunmi J. OLAYEMI, Sophie NOCK-ANYEBE, "Evaluation of Novel co-processed excipient for fast disintegration of aspirin tablet formulations", *Journal of PHARMACY AND BIORESOURCES*, 2021 Vol. 18 no. 1, 1-11.
18. Bhawana Dhakal, Jaybir Kumar Thakur, Reema Kumari Mahato, Ishwori Rawat, D. C. Rabin, Rahul Rana Chhetri, Kedar Prasad Shah, Atul Adhikari, and Jitendra Pandey, "Formulation of Ebastine Fast-Disintegrating Tablet Using Coprocessed Superdisintegrants and Evaluation of Quality Control Parameters", *The Scientific World Journal*, 2022, 1-13.

HOW TO CITE: Pranjal Borse*, Manoj Bari, Formulation Optimization & Evaluation of Co-Processed Excipients for Orally Disintegrating Tablet of Bilastine, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 2945-2961.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15710893>

